

Project-based Learning Through a Culturally Responsive Lens: Enhancing Learners' English Literacy Skills

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Abstract: Learning materials are tools necessary for carrying out educational activities. Preliminary studies showed that there is still a lack of development in learning materials. This study evaluated the development of an integrated project-based learning model based on CRT to enhance literacy skills, which has been tested for validity and effectiveness. The research method used in the research and development model. The research is located in the partner school of city field and Serdang District Bedagai. Thus, the sampling technique is used as a nonprobability sample and is carried out in a partner school of 120 students. The results were obtained through research on the learning model project based on learning integrated culturally responsive teaching of products carried out by expert validators, and the validation data for teaching materials is obtained from the evaluation conducted by a validator on the content material and design of the teaching materials resulting valid, practical and effective module. Research also showed that the project-based learning model integrated with CRT is effectively applied to students in terms of their English literacy skills.

Anahtar Sözcükler:

Eğitim
Kültürel olarak
duyarlı öğretim
Proje tabanlı
öğrenme
İngilizce
okuryazarlık
becerileri
Endonezya

Kültürel Duyarlılık Perspektifinden Proje Tabanlı Öğrenme: Öğrenci Katılımını ve Kapsayıcı Eğitimi Güçlendirme

Özet: Öğretim materyalleri, eğitim faaliyetlerinin yürütülmesinde gerekli temel araçlardır ve yapılan ön çalışmalar bu materyallerin geliştirilmesinde eksiklikler olduğunu ortaya koymaktadır. Bu araştırma, okuryazarlık becerilerini geliştirmek amacıyla kültürel duyarlı öğretim temelli entegre bir proje tabanlı öğrenme modeli geliştirmiş ve bu modelin geçerlilik ile etkililik testlerini değerlendirmiştir. Araştırma ve geliştirme modelinin kullanıldığı bu çalışma, Medan Şehri ve Serdang Bedagai Bölgesi'ndeki iş birliği halinde olan okullarda yürütülmüş olup, amaçlı örnekleme yöntemiyle seçilen 120 öğrencinin katılımıyla gerçekleştirilmiştir. Uzman validasyon süreci sonucunda geliştirilen öğretim materyallerinin içerik ve tasarım açısından geçerli olduğu, uygulanabilir (pratik) nitelik taşıdığı ve öğrencilerin İngilizce okuryazarlık becerileri üzerinde etkili olduğu tespit edilmiştir. Araştırma bulguları, kültürel duyarlı öğretime entegre edilmiş proje tabanlı öğrenme modelinin geçerli, kullanışlı ve akademik olarak etkili bir yaklaşım olduğunu ve öğrencilerin dil becerilerini anlamlı düzeyde geliştirdiğini ortaya koymuştur.

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1. Introduction

The rapid advancements in science and technology in the last few decades have complex societal implications. The development of the era of globalization has impacted the rise of culture and cultural identity worldwide and in Indonesia. These developments have led to dramatic changes in the perspectives and values attributed to nationalism (Almarza et al., 2015). Multiculturalism, multiple identities, and cultural shifting are now social facts in our lives in every domain (Tan, 2008). Given that education is a dynamic process that evolves alongside societal changes (Pigozzi, 2007; UNESCO, 2014), learners should be instilled with the necessary knowledge and ability to be agents of change, character, and culture in the face of future challenges. As demographics of today's societies have been rapidly changing due to various political, cultural, or commercial variables (e.g., the Internet, science, immigration etc.), conventional teaching methods and practices would fail in such contexts where classrooms involve various culturally different learners (Banks & McGee Banks, 2016; Gay, 2002).

Culturally responsive teaching (CRT) emerged as a response to this need, referring to “using the cultural knowledge, prior experiences, frames of reference, and performance styles of ethnically diverse students to make learning encounters more relevant to and effective for them” (Gay, 2010, p. 31). Accordingly, CRT aims to imbue learners with essential knowledge and skills to act harmoniously with mainstream culture while keeping their cultural identities and native languages (Muniz, 2019; Siwatu, 2007). As classrooms grow increasingly diverse, integrating CRT with innovative pedagogical approaches like project-based learning also becomes essential to enhance student engagement and foster inclusivity and equity (Banks & McGee Banks, 2016; Gay, 2010). Accordingly, culturally responsive teachers tend to be more aware of the critical role that various aspects of culture play in learning and academic achievement (Kaygısız, 2023; Ladson-Billings, 1995; Siwatu, 2007; Zorba, 2020) in that they are able recognize and appreciate the contribution of different cultural groups is critical in fostering students' academic development (Gay, 2010; Ialuna et al., 2024).

One model that connects learning with students' culture is the culturally responsive transformative teaching model, which consists of five phases: self-identification, cultural understanding, collaboration, critical thinking, and transformative construction. Culturally responsive transformative teaching is adapted from CRT, a learning approach that utilizes cultural knowledge, students' experiences, and learning styles to create more meaningful learning (Bassey, 2016; Kim & Slapac, 2015). Teaching materials are an important component for both students and teachers. The availability of appropriate teaching materials will assist students in achieving their educational goals and essential competencies. Therefore, these materials are crucial components in learning activities, especially in implementing learning, where teaching materials are developed according to the needs of teachers and students (Kim & Slapac, 2015).

The changes have also led to the emergence of 21st-century skills that include critical thinking and problem-solving, communication, collaboration, and creative and innovative skills. Collaborative skills are defined as the collaboration of individuals to clarify differences of views and knowledge and actively participate in discussions by providing input, listening, and supporting each other (Rahmawati et al., 2020). Less active students tend to be unable to express their feelings or opinions. Some students still violate school orders, especially the violation of the right to discipline, such as when entering school and assault during classroom learning. Classrooms of the 21st century are characterized by the increasing diversity of student populations in K-12 schools (Ateh & Ryan, 2023), while teacher demographics

remain relatively stable. This diversity gap between teachers and students may potentially lead to cultural conflicts because teachers may not always understand the cultural context of the classroom behavior in the teaching and learning of their students (Thijs *et al.*, 2025).

With all these in mind, project-based learning comes to the fore at this point; as Rehman *et al.* (2024) underline, this way of learning acts as a catalyst for 21st-century skills and student engagement. Besides, the project-based learning model encourages students to create and produce authentic projects that foster a variety of student competencies (Apriansyah *et al.*, 2024). This approach involves students actively participating in the learning process. Moreover, Amamou and Cheniti-Belcadhi (2018) state that the project-based learning model is another educational approach that can enhance students' attitudes, knowledge, and skill competencies. Recent studies revealed that project-based learning is often used to replace traditional teaching methods where the teacher is the center of learning, increasing learning outcomes and problem-solving skills of students (Cirit-Işikligil & Günay, 2022; Kemalglu-Er & Sahin, 2022; Mudiono, 2024; Zhou, 2023). In addition to learning models, learning approaches can also support learning and improve the quality of education, especially in knowledge and skill competencies. This can be supported, for example, by combining them with CRT. CRT (e.g., Kaygısız, 2023; Koukoulidis *et al.*, 2024; Meihami, 2023; Şenbayrak & Ortaçtepe Hart, 2024; Zorba, 2020) and project-based learning (e.g., Kemalglu-Er & Sahin, 2022; Mudiono, 2024) have been gaining much currency in the field of foreign language teaching, focusing on different aspects or issues related to teaching and learning. However, there is a paucity of research integrating project-based learning with CRT.

A critical gap exists in current English language teaching materials, particularly those integrating North Sumatran local culture within a project-based learning framework. In line with this, the present study aims to investigate culturally responsive, project-based instruction on students' English literacy skills and provide insights into this way of teaching.

2. Method

2.1. Research Design

This study is based on a qualitative and quantitative research design, collecting and analyzing non-numerical and numerical data to describe, explain, predict, or control the phenomenon (Gay *et al.*, 2015; Cohen *et al.*, 2018). As for the instructional design, the ADDIE model (i.e., analysis, design, development, implementation, and evaluation) was employed, which is a teaching model allowing practitioners, program developers, and researchers to design short- or long-term instructional implementations (Spatioti *et al.*, 2022). In the first step (analysis), the current situation is analyzed to understand and identify the gap to be filled. In the second step (development), informed decisions are made to design the learning; in the third step, the program and the necessary materials are developed. The fourth step is the implementation of the designed model. In the last step, educational activities are evaluated thoroughly (Reinbold, 2013; Spatioti *et al.*, 2022; Van Rooij, 2010).

2.2. Participants

This study was conducted with the participation of 120 students learning English in two groups from two different state universities in the Serdang and Bedagai districts of Indonesia. Convenience sampling was used to select research participants. This method allows researchers to collect data from a sample regarding accessibility, willingness to participate, geographic proximity, and availability during a particular timeframe (Stratton, 2021; Teddlie & Yu, 2007). Therefore, the sample does not represent any group apart from itself, and the

aim is not to make generalizations about the wider population (Cohen et al., 2018), as these participants construct a culturally heterogeneous group in line with the premises of CRT (Lavigne et al., 2022).

2.3. Data Collection and Analysis

Quantitative data were collected through a 5-point Likert questionnaire developed by the researchers. The questionnaire involved five sections, focusing on the introduction, content, learning, task, and language aspects. The questionnaire was administered two times as a pretest and posttest. All participants filled out the questionnaire. Data were analyzed through the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS version 23), focusing on descriptive and inferential statistics. As seen in Table 1, a normal distribution was found after conducting the normality test (Field, 2018). Additionally, Levene’s test for equality of variances indicated no significant differences between groups, confirming homogeneity of variance, which supports the appropriateness of parametric tests assuming equal variances (see Table 2).

Table 1.

Table Normality Test Results

Kolmogorov-Smirnov Test			
		AB1	AB2
N		60	60
Normal Parameters ^{a,b}	Mean	.0000000	.0000000
	SD	2.21337003	2.16969921
Most Extreme Differences	Absolute	.089	.066
	Positive	.089	.066
	Negative	-.071	-.050
	Test Statistic	.089	.066
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)		.200 ^{c,d}	.200 ^{c,d}

Additionally, Levene’s test for equality of variances indicated no significant differences between groups, confirming homogeneity of variance, which supports the appropriateness of parametric tests assuming equal variances (See Table 2).

Table 2.

Homogeneity Test Results

Homogeneity Test					
		Levene Statistic	df1	df2	Sig.
Group 1	Based on Mean	.350	1	118	.555
	Based on Median	.196	1	118	.659
	Based on the Median and with adjusted df	.196	1	112.747	.659
	Based on trimmed mean	.277	1	118	.600
Group 2	Based on Mean	.947	1	118	.332
	Based on Median	.616	1	118	.434
	Based on the Median and with adjusted df	.616	1	109.705	.434
	Based on trimmed mean	.819	1	118	.367

3. Findings

3.1. Need Analysis

At this stage, the activities involved observing and interviewing teachers and students regarding the fundamental issues that posed challenges for teachers in improving the performance of both teachers and students in the learning process. The teaching materials

used by the students and the learning strategies commonly employed by the teachers in the classroom were also analyzed. The low interest in learning among students is due to their lack of understanding of the material and their still weak literacy skills. An analysis of the students is conducted to understand the problem they face regarding the teaching materials used and the teaching strategies employed by the teacher during the classroom learning process. Learning in the classroom was usually done through lectures, which made it monotonous, so the students got bored as they listened to and understood what the teacher presented. Furthermore, the teacher did not use interactive learning media, especially since no additional teaching materials, such as project-based learning materials, were integrated with CRT.

3.2. Integrating Module Project-based Learning with CRT

The goal was to design educational materials resulting in project-based learning resources. It begins with the preparation of content that consists of several activities. Each step included adhered to the syntax of project-based learning. The components of integrated CRT and project-based teaching materials were similar to other teaching materials, generally consisting of cover, module identity, preface, target users, description, final learning objectives, and instruction for teaching materials.

3.2.1. Task analysis activities

The activities carried out in task analysis were to identify and select materials. The aim was to determine the materials so students could understand them. The material for the project-based learning teaching materials was genre text writing, such as hortatory text. Regarding the activities in the teaching materials, each activity included one or two practice questions that students must complete to reinforce their understanding of the material.

3.2.2. Design Phase

Two types of design were conducted: the design of teaching materials and the design tools. First, designing a project-based learning teaching material model that was integrated with CRT. The design of the first stage consisted of developing ideas, conducting studies, establishing the theories and concepts underpinning the content and construction of the teaching material model, and selecting the book format. The English teaching materials were designed using a project-based learning framework. The design included the title and identity of the instructional model, along with clear learning instructions to help students navigate the materials effectively. It also outlined the target competencies and learning indicators to define expected outcomes. The project-based learning was integrated into the learning process, while step-by-step tasks and activities guided students through project work. Finally, learning strategies were integrated to enhance engagement and comprehension, ensuring a cohesive and student-centered approach. Designing tools for a project-based learning teaching material model integrated with CRT. There are six indicators to designing tools, for example, the visual design aspect of image suitability. In the project-based learning stage, teachers and students were engaged in activities. At this stage, the teacher acted as a facilitator in the project activities undertaken by the students. Moreover, the students participated directly in the project, from preparing tools and materials to compiling reports. Therefore, project-based learning was developed based on several opinions presented below.

Table 3.
Stages and Activities

Stages	Teacher' Activities	Student' Activities
Fundamental question	The teacher posed the fundamental question to the students for starting the learning activity using the Curipod application.	The students answer the fundamental question posed by the teacher.
Designing project planning	The teacher guides the students in creating a product based on the teaching materials: hortatory explanatory texts. The teacher sets the deadline for the project of creating a hortatory explanatory text to be completed by the students.	The students create a hortatory explanatory product.
Scheduling	The teacher sets the deadline for the project of creating a hortatory explanatory text to be completed by the students.	The students attempt to finish the project within the specified time.
Monitoring students in project progress	The teacher monitors the progress of the projects being worked on by students.	The students complete the creation of a hortatory explanatory text with the teacher's guidance.
Testing the result	The teacher asks the students to test the project's results, which they have completed as a hortatory explanatory text using Curipod and Canva.	The students try to determine whether the product they have created is successful or not.
Evaluating	The teacher asks the students to evaluate the products that they have worked on and complete the evaluation questions.	The students present the result of their hortatory explanatory text.

3.2.3. *The Validity Instrument of Model Project-based Learning Integrated CRT*

There were two stages of assessment: expert validation and field testing. Expert validators carried out the result of the product, and the validation data for the teaching materials was obtained from the evaluation conducted by expert validators on the teaching materials' content, material, and design.

Table 4.

The Validity Instrument of Model Project-based Learning Integrated CRT

Aspects	Score (%)	Valid Category	Interpretation
Introduction Aspect	3.50	Very Valid (3.5-4.0)	Excellent clarity and relevance
Content Aspect	2.90	Valid (2.5-3.49)	Needs clearer examples
Learning Aspect	3.0	Valid (2.5-3.49)	Meets standards
Task Aspect	3.15	Valid (2.5-3.49)	Well-structured activities
Language Aspect	3.50	Very Valid (3.5-4.0)	Clear and appropriate language
Total (Average)	3.21	Valid (2.5-3.49)	Overall valid for use

As can be seen in Table 4, the validity assessment of the project-based learning model integrated with culturally responsive teaching involved expert validation across five key aspects: introduction, content, learning, task, and language. The results indicated that all aspects scored within the "Valid" range (2.90–3.50 out of a possible 4), with an overall average score of 3.21, showing the overall validity. The introduction and language aspects received the highest scores (3.50), suggesting strong clarity and alignment with objectives. The content aspect scored slightly lower (2.90) than the other aspects due to insufficient clarity in examples that illustrate the material. Despite this minor limitation, the content remains categorized as "Very Valid," reinforcing the module's overall suitability. The Task (3.15) and Learning (3.0) aspects also performed well, indicating effective design in

instructional activities and pedagogical alignment. These results demonstrate that the module is ready for field testing, though the content examples could be refined further to enhance clarity.

3.3. Quantitative Findings

English literacy skills are rated with a maximum score of 25. From the data, the average score of students from Group 1 was 17.58 in the pretest and increased to 21.48 in the posttest. Similarly, the average score in Group 2 increased from 15.77 to 21.15. Additionally, the paired samples t-tests revealed statistically significant differences in both groups following the intervention. For Group 1, posttest scores ($M = 21.48$, $SD = 2.20$) showed a significant increase from pretest scores ($M = 17.58$, $SD = 2.53$), $t(59) = 12.07$, $p < .001$, with a large effect size ($d = 1.56$). Similarly, Group 2 demonstrated substantial improvement, with posttest scores ($M = 21.15$, $SD = 2.40$) significantly higher than pretest scores ($M = 15.76$, $SD = 2.81$), $t(59) = 14.92$, $p < .001$, showing a very large effect size ($d = 2.14$). These results indicate that the intervention was effective for both groups, with Group 2 exhibiting greater improvement as evidenced by the higher mean difference and larger effect size. The consistently significant p-values ($p < .001$) and large effect sizes suggest robust intervention effects across groups. Based on these results, it can be seen that there is a statistically significant improvement with meaningful effect sizes in students' English literacy skills by implementing CRT-integrated project-based learning materials.

Table 5.

Pretest and Posttest Results

	N	Min.	Max.	M	SD	t value	p value	d value
Pretest (Group 1)	60	13.00	25.00	17.58	2.53	12.07	.000*	1.56
Posttest (Group 1)	60	16.00	25.00	21.48	2.20			
Pretest (Group 2)	60	12.00	24.00	15.76	2.81	14.92	.000*	2.14
Posttest (Group 2)	60	15.00	25.00	21.15	2.40			

* $p < .01$

4. Discussion and Conclusion

This study focused on CRT-integrated project-based learning in terms of the process of developing the implementation and the end results of the implementation, which is improving learners' English literacy skills in the Indonesian context. Accordingly, findings revealed that the ADDIE model for implementation design yielded positive results and a valid implementation, particularly for integrating CRT with project-based learning (Branch, 2009; Gay, 2010; Stoller & Myers, 2020). The project-based learning model was effectively implemented in learning activities, allowing students to develop their skills during the learning process. This also indicated that the project-based learning model can be integrated with the CRT approach. This aimed to equip students to face real-world challenges per the pillar of Indonesian education, which is learning to know, do, and develop holistically. These findings about project-based learning concur with those previous research revealed. Accordingly, findings showed that the CRT-integrated project-based learning implementation model may be an alternative to traditional teaching methods where the teacher is the center of learning, increasing learning outcomes and problem-solving skills of students (Kemaloglu-Er & Sahin, 2022; Mudiono, 2024; Zhou, 2023).

In line with CRT, the implementation module covers various cultural aspects of genre writing, such as student culture, traditional houses, traditional clothing, and traditional dances relevant to learners' cultural backgrounds. Using teaching materials that can effectively integrate content project-based learning and CRT facilitates students in mastering the competencies of literacy achievement (Ialuna et al., 2024; Siwatu, 2007). Integrated project-based learning with CRT also created a strong learning model encouraging inclusivity, engagement, and meaningful learning (Bassey, 2016; Kim & Slapac, 2015). Findings align with the notion that project-based learning encouraged students to actively explore real-world problems and develop solutions, encouraging critical thinking and collaborative work (Thomas, 2000; Krajcik & Shin, 2014). Combined with CRT, this model enhanced learning experiences by embedding learners' cultural backgrounds into the projects. This integration ensures that students learn more about what they are learning. For instance, the project can be designed to address challenges specific to the community or incorporate traditional practices and knowledge, improving students' academic skills and strengthening their cultural identity. Lastly, the quantitative results showed statistically significant differences with high effect sizes. This finding underpins that the intervention had meaningful and practical impacts beyond statistical significance.

Based on these findings, this study suggests several implications for teaching course design. First, CRT and project-based learning often yield positive results. Therefore, curricula, teaching materials, and pedagogies should be revised accordingly in contexts where culturally and linguistically different learners exist. In line with this, teacher education programs also aim to increase teacher candidates' awareness, knowledge, and skills related to CRT and project-based learning. Second, systematic approaches should be followed (e.g., the ADDIE model) while preparing any instructional implementation. This study used the ADDIE model, yet other models allow course designers to prepare syllabuses or any other interventions systematically. Third, studies are needed to investigate the process and products of CRT-integrated project-based learning in different contexts. Therefore, further studies may focus on implementing similar models employing different research designs and data collection tools. Lastly, this study has certain limitations. First, it was conducted with a small group of research participants. Therefore, the results may change at larger scales. Secondly, this study was conducted in the Indonesian context, and results of similar studies from different contexts may change considering political, ideological, and cultural differences.

Ethical Issues

This study was conducted with the approval of the Ethics Committee of Universitas Muslim Nusantara Al Washliyah University. Written informed consent was obtained from all participants involved in the study.

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Conflict of Interest

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

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